

27 ABSTRACT

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29 The high cost and restricted availability of black truffle spore inoculum for controlled mycorrhiza formation
30 of host trees produced for truffle orchards worldwide encourage the search for more efficient and sustainable
31 inoculation methods that can be applied globally. In this study, we evaluated the potential of the nurse plant
32 method for the controlled inoculation of *Quercus cerris* and *Quercus robur* with *Tuber melanosporum* by
33 mycorrhizal networks in pot cultures. Pine bark compost, adjusted to pH7.8 by liming, was used as substrate
34 for all assays. Initially, *Q. robur* seedlings were inoculated with truffle spores and cultured for 12 months.
35 After this period, the plants presenting 74 % mycorrhizal fine roots were transferred to larger containers.
36 Nurse plants were used for two treatments of two different nursling species: five sterilized acorns or five 45-
37 day-old, axenically grown *Q. robur* or *Q. cerris* seedlings, planted in containers around the nurse plant. After
38 6 months, colonized nursling plant root tips showed that mycorrhiza formation by *T. melanosporum* was
39 higher than 45 % in the seedlings tested, with the most successful nursling combination being *Q. cerris*
40 seedlings, reaching 81 % colonization. Bulk identification of *T. melanosporum* mycorrhizae was based on
41 morphological and anatomical features and confirmed by sequencing of the internal transcribed spacer region
42 of the ribosomal DNA of selected root tips. Our results show that the nurse plant method yields attractive
43 rates of mycorrhiza formation by the Périgord black truffle and suggest that establishing and maintaining
44 common mycorrhizal networks in pot cultures enables sustained use of the initial spore inoculum.

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47 KEYWORDS

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49 Périgord black truffle, pot culture, *Quercus robur*, *Quercus cerris*, bark compost, liming.

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65 INTRODUCTION

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67 The edible fruiting bodies of the Périgord black truffle (*Tuber melanosporum* Vittad) are an important
68 economical, social, and ecological resource in its natural distribution area and 47° N, approximately (García
69 et al. 2007; Reyna 2000, 2007). Their limited production and their highly appreciated organoleptic properties
70 are the main reasons for the long history of these truffles as an expensive and exclusive dietary supplement
71 (García-Montero et al. 2007; Oliach et al. 2008; Águeda et al. 2010). However, overharvesting as well as loss
72 and degradation of natural habitats by man-made and natural causes have drastically reduced productivity in
73 natural truffle woodlands during the past decades (Honrubia et al. 2006; Reyna 2007; Pereira et al. 2010). As
74 a consequence, methods of truffle culture based on controlled mycorrhiza formation of adequate host trees
75 with this obligatory ectomycorrhizal fungus (Honrubia et al. 2006; Pereira et al. 2010) have been developed
76 and improved by international research groups (Sáez 1991; Meotto 1994; Reyna and Colinas 2007; Hall et al.
77 2009). Successful truffle culture requires careful selection of plant and fungal material as well as of soil or
78 culture substrate (Palazón and Barriuso 2007). As the preparation and establishment of truffle orchards is cost
79 and time intensive, there is a need to optimize the procedure in order to increase efficiency, especially of the
80 production of large numbers of inoculated host plants in nursery. A key factor for sustainable and efficient
81 production of truffle mycorrhizae is the source of inoculum; traditionally, spore inoculum as well as cultured
82 mycelium has been used (Iotti et al. 2002; Santelices and Palfner 2010). The first method is easy to apply but
83 is typically limited by the seasonal availability of natural growing fruiting bodies, deterioration of the
84 inoculum by storage or long-distance transport, and increasing market values of wild truffles; also, spore
85 inoculum is not always pure and may introduce unwanted adventitious fungal species which compete with, or
86 even displace, the desired truffle species during mycorrhiza formation in nursery and field (Bonito et al. 2011;
87 Turgeman et al. 2012). Contrarily, the mycelium method provides a constant supply of pure inoculum when
88 produced under the corresponding laboratory conditions but requires cost-intensive infrastructure for strain
89 isolation, maintenance, and multiplication. An attractive alternative is the nurse plant method where host
90 plants, initially inoculated with spore inoculum or cultured mycelium of the selected fungal species, are
91 transplanted to large containers which allow the development of an extensive mycorrhizal system (colonized
92 roots and mycelium) in the substrate. A defined number of axenically grown nursling host plants are then
93 planted into the same containers around the nurse plant where their developing fine roots can connect to the
94 established truffle mycelium, forming a common mycorrhizal network. The aim of this study was to evaluate
95 the potential of the nurse plant method in assays of controlled colonization of oak fine roots with Périgord
96 black truffle, using both seeds and previously grown seedlings of *Quercus cerris* L. and *Quercus robur* L. as
97 targets

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100 MATERIAL AND METHODS

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102 Initial Inoculum

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104 Fruiting bodies of *T. melanosporum* were collected at natural sites in Castilla la Mancha (Spain) and
105 identified by their diagnostic macroscopic and microscopic features (Chevalier and Frochot 1997; Rioussset et
106 al. 2001) before being dried at room temperature, crushed, and preserved for the subsequent inoculation of
107 nurse plants.

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109 Preparation and inoculation of nurse plants

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111 Acorns of adult trees of *Q. robur* were collected in Los Ángeles, Chile, and stratified under moist conditions
112 and 4 ° C during 2 months. Before being planted in 260-mL containers, the seeds were surface sterilized with
113 10 % sodium hypochlorite solution during 15 min. The substrate consisted of composted bark of *Pinus radiata*
114 D. Don, previously autoclaved at 121 °C for 1 h during three consecutive days, and limed with Magnecal 15
115 (Inacal Company, Copiapo, Chile) until a pH of 7.8. After 45 days, the emerged seedlings were inoculated
116 with a spore suspension of *T. melanosporum* at a level of approx 10⁶ spores/plant, injected directly into the
117 root system (Honrubia et al. 1992; Brundrett et al. 1996; Palazón and Barriuso 2007). After that, plants were
118 kept under controlled conditions in a growth chamber (daily photoperiod of 8 h, relative air humidity 55±5 %,
119 air temperature 24±1°C) during 6 months. After that period, the pot cultures were transferred to a greenhouse
120 for another 6 months where aseptic conditions were maintained to avoid contamination, and watering was
121 performed to field capacity level once or twice a week, according to the plants state of development.

122 These plants are referred to as nurse plants according to their function as inoculum source for the nursling
123 plants. Evaluation of their mycorrhizal status was performed 6 and 12 months after their inoculation,
124 according to Palazón and Barriuso (2007). Segments of long roots with adhering short roots were carefully
125 extracted from three different depths of the root system of each nurse plant (proximally, intermediately, and
126 distally in relation to the root collar) and cut in segments of 2 to 3 cm length. Three hundred root tips,
127 randomly selected from these segments, were screened under a dissecting microscope for mycorrhiza
128 formation. For the final evaluation, 12 plants from each treatment were sampled the same way, and only the
129 number of observed root tips was raised to 600 per plant. The results were expressed in percent of
130 mycorrhizal root tips.

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132 Establishment of nursling plants

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134 After 12 months, 16 nurse plants with confirmed colonization of their fine roots by *T. melanosporum* were
135 transplanted in 8-L containers with the same type of substrate previously used. The assay was divided in four
136 groups (n= 4): two groups of each *Quercus* species (*Q. robur* and *Q. cerris*, respectively) with either acorns
137 (A) or 45-day-old seedlings (S), as targets for mycorrhiza formation. In each container, five sterilized acorns

138 or five seedlings grown axenically in the same substrate type as the nurse plants were planted at 10 cm
139 distance from the nurse plant. After 2 and 6 months, the root systems of both types of nursling plants (A and
140 S) were screened for presence of *T. melanosporum* mycorrhizas.

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142 Identification of mycorrhizae by morphological features

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144 Fresh mycorrhizal root tips were observed under a dissecting microscope (Olympus SZ2-ILST) and
145 compound microscope (Olympus CX32) and documented by microphotographs using a Moticam 2000 2.0
146 Mpixel digital camera. Morphological and anatomical features such as color and surface structures of whole
147 mycorrhizae as well as cellular shape of cystidia and mantle layers were determined according to Agerer
148 (1986, 1991) and compared with reference descriptions of *T. melanosporum* ectomycorrhizae (Zambonelli et
149 al. 1993; Rauscher and Chevalier 1995; Rauscher et al. 1995; De Miguel and Sáez 1997; Domínguez et al.
150 2005; Reyna and De Miguel 2007; Sáez and De Miguel 2008). Line drawings of diagnostic details were made
151 with a Leitz Dialux compound microscope, equipped with a camera lucida drawing device at $\times 1,000$
152 magnification of water-mounted, fresh specimens. Selected reference specimens of whole ectomycorrhizae
153 were preserved in 2 % CTAB or 70 % ethanol at 4 °C for subsequent molecular analysis.

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155 Molecular identification of mycorrhizae

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157 Two samples consisting of three to five mycorrhizae previously assigned to *T. melanosporum* based on
158 morphological characteristics were randomly selected from *Q. robur* and *Q. cerris* roots for molecular
159 analyses. Genomic DNA from these root tips was isolated using the E.Z.N.A. Fungal DNA miniprep kit
160 (Omega Bio-Tek, Doraville, GA, USA) without mercaptoethanol. Non-mycorrhizal roots from *Q. robur* were
161 used as negative controls. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was performed using PuReTaq Ready-to-Go PCR
162 beads (GE Healthcare, Little Chalfont, Buckinghamshire, UK). The internal transcribed spacer region (ITS)
163 of the nuclear ribosomal DNA (nrDNA) including the 5.8S ribosomal subunit was amplified using the fungal
164 specific primer ITS1F (Gardes and Bruns 1993) and the eukaryotic primer ITS4 (White et al. 1990), following
165 cycling conditions proposed by Martín and Winka (2000). A positive control consisting of DNA from a *T.*
166 *melanosporum* ascoma and a negative control without DNA were included. Amplicons were visualized in 2 %
167 agarose gels stained with SYBR® safe (Invitrogen, Eugene, OR, USA) under visible light. PCR products
168 were then cleaned using the E.Z.N.A.® Cycle-Pure kit (Omega Bio-Tek). Two sequencing reactions were
169 carried out corresponding to both primers utilized in the amplification. Sequencher (Gene Codes Corporation,
170 Ann Arbor, MI, USA) was used to identify the consensus sequence from the two strands of the ITS-nrDNA of
171 each isolate. Obtained sequences were compared with other DNA sequences in GenBank (NCBI) by
172 megablast searches (Altschul et al. 1997). ITS sequences were included in

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174 GenBank under the accession numbers GU810152 and GU810153.

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176 Assay design and statistics

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178 A factorial experimental design, using host tree species (*Q. robur* and *Q. cerris*) and initial state of nursling
179 plants (acorn–seedling) as factors with two levels each and four replicas per treatment, was used. The effect of
180 each separate factor as well as combined factors and interactions was evaluated by using two-way ANOVA;
181 separation of means was performed by using a Tukey test ($p < 0.05$) for multiple comparisons (Steel and
182 Torrie 1989). The program Statistica 6.0 was used.

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185 RESULTS

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187 Six months after initial treatment of the nurse plants with spore inoculum, *Q. robur* seedlings showed 53 %
188 ectomycorrhizal fine roots which increased up to 74 % after 12 months (Fig. 1a) when nurse plants were
189 transplanted to larger containers. Two months after the nurslings (A and S) had been established (Fig. 2a),
190 abundant mycorrhiza formation by *T. melanosporum* on nurslings was observed in both hosts (*Q. cerris* and
191 *Q. robur*), with best results being observed in seedlings, independent of the tree species (Fig. 2b). Figure 1b
192 shows that after 6 months, *Q. cerris* seedlings yielded the highest colonization rate (81 %) in comparison to
193 the A group (53 %); in *Q. robur*, the corresponding values were 68 and 45 %, respectively. Differences by
194 treatment were statistically significant within each oak species, but not between species.

195 Mycorrhizal systems were monopodial with lateral, mostly simple ramifications (Fig. 2b, c) and of reddish
196 brown or dark brown color, changing with age. The characteristic 90°-angle-ramified cystidia were regularly
197 found, mostly in patches, on the mantle surface (Figs. 2c–e and 3c). Mantle scrapings revealed a pseudo-
198 parenchymatic epidermoid cell pattern of the outer mantle layer, covered by a superficial, wide meshed and
199 patchy net of elongated and ramified hyphae from which the cystidia emerge (Figs. 2f and 3a, b). ITS
200 sequences obtained from mycorrhizae formed by both oak species confirmed their identity as black truffle,
201 showing maximum similarity with *T. melanosporum* sequences from GenBank. No other adventitious fungal
202 colonizers could be detected on the observed ectomycorrhizal roots. As could be expected, the low pH of
203 initially untreated substrate (pH4.9; Table 1) was inadequate for efficient colonization of *Quercus* spp. fine
204 roots by *T. melanosporum*, whereas gradual liming with Magnecal 15 up to pH 7.8 yielded high colonization
205 rates. It should be noted that the content of organic matter of the used substrate (31.5 %) is higher than in
206 other substrate types usually used for controlled mycorrhiza formation by *T. melanosporum* (see discussion).

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208 Increase of pH caused a decrease in levels of N, P, and K, but an increase of Ca, Mg, and CICE in the
209 substrate. Also, an increase of conductivity from 0.24 to 0.30 dS m⁻¹ could be observed, whereas the C/N
210 ratio diminished (Table 1).

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212 DISCUSSION

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214 Efficient monospecific mycorrhiza formation in nursery plants is the most essential condition for
215 establishment of a viable commercial truffle orchard (Cartié et al. 1999; Palazón and Barriuso 2007; Pereira et
216 al. 2010). For inoculation of host seedlings with *T. melanosporum*, spore inoculum has been most commonly
217 applied, either dry (powdering) or suspended in water (injection and root immersion), but also previously
218 produced (detached) mycorrhizal roots have been shown to be an adequate inoculum source (Cartié et al.
219 1999; Palazón and Barriuso 2007), in some cases even more efficient than spore inoculum (Amnón et al.
220 2006). Spore-based methods require the use of considerable quantities of mature fruiting bodies during each
221 inoculation ranging between 1 and 5 g of truffle (fresh weight) per plant in order to obtain a satisfactory
222 colonization rate (Domínguez et al. 2005; Palazón and Barriuso 2007). The nurse plant method allows a more
223 cost-efficient and sustained use of the initial inoculum, as long as axenic conditions are maintained, and is
224 based on the concept that an initially inoculated host plant (nurse plant) is given enough time and space to
225 develop an extensive mycorrhizal root system. Later, a determined number of sterile-grown, new seedlings
226 (nurslings) are planted around the nurse plant where their fine roots can connect to the established truffle
227 mycelium and form a common mycorrhizal network in larger containers. These nurslings may eventually be
228 transplanted to nursery or field or be used as new nurse plants to rapidly expand the production system. Our
229 results show that it is possible to obtain regular rates of mycorrhiza formation above 45 % about 18 months
230 after the initiation of the setup, even reaching 81 % in seedlings of *Q. cerris* and that the nurse plant method is
231 viable as suggested by Palazón and Barriuso (2007), although its performance under long-term commercial
232 conditions remains to be tested.

233 Although in our assay, the nurse plants were cultured 12 months before the nurslings were established;
234 mycorrhiza formation in the latter to the levels indicated above took only 6 months. This result compares
235 favorably to other studies where similar results were obtained after more than 8 months (Cartié et al. 1999;
236 Domínguez et al. 2005). Even after just 2 months, mycorrhizal root tips formed by *T. melanosporum* could be
237 regularly observed in both nursling species (*Q. robur* and *Q. cerris*) and both treatments (A and S). This quick
238 response can be attributed to the higher inoculum potential of the established, active mycelium of the nurse
239 plant. This may outperform spore inoculum at this stage because spores would have to germinate and form an
240 extensive mycelium first. Other variables that affect the time required for mycorrhiza formation, apart from
241 the inoculum type, are substrate temperature and other culture conditions and, especially, the combination of
242 myco- and phytobiont species (Gent et al. 2009) as confirmed by this study; *Q. cerris* usually performs very
243 well as mycorrhizal host for *T. melanosporum* (Pinkas et al. 2000; Pereira et al. 2010).

244 Regarding the specific substrate requirements of *T. melanosporum* in terms of pH, ratio between mineral and
245 organic components as well as other chemical, physical, and biological factors (Palazón and Barriuso 2007),
246 various substrate types have been tested during the development of truffle culture, ranging from natural soil
247 from truffle woodlands to different types and mixtures of natural and artificial components such as soil, peat,
248 perlite, vermiculite, sand, dolomite, and varieties of compost. The results of our assay confirm that compost of

249 P. radiata bark, a cheap byproduct of forestry industry in various parts of the world, is an adequate substrate
250 after an adjustment of its natural pH of
251 4.9 by application of lime such as Magnecal 15 which consists of 95 % CaCO₃ and other mineral components
252 like Mg, CaO, SO₃, K, and Na₂O which add important micronutrients during the nursery phase of the
253 inoculated seedlings. It should be considered that incomplete composting of the pine bark may have a
254 negative impact on seed germination and seedling growth and thus hamper the establishment of mycorrhizal
255 symbiosis. For this study, substrate pH was adjusted to 7.8, value which has been considered optimal
256 for synthesis of *T. melanosporum* mycorrhizas by several research groups (Cartié et al. 1999; Domínguez et al.
257 2005; Palazón and Barriuso 2007; Santelices and Palfner 2010). According to Callot (1999) and Bradshaw
258 (2005), natural calcareous soils of European black truffle habitats, which are frequently used pure or mixed
259 for black truffle culture, are characterized by relatively low levels of organic matter (up to 8 %), which is
260 much less than in the substrate used for this assay (31.5 %). Conductivity reflects the concentration of soil
261 solution salts in the substrate; a high conductivity may be an effect of the substrate material but also of
262 excessive fertilization, which can negatively affect plant performance and mycorrhizal formation. Low levels
263 of this parameter are recommended for truffle culture; in fact, natural truffle grounds have not been found in
264 saline or chalky soils (García et al. 2007). During the liming process, we measured an increase of conductivity
265 from 0.24 to 0.30 dS m⁻¹ in the substrate, within the recommended values for truffle culture.

266 Macro- and micromorphology of the analyzed mycorrhizal structures (color and shape of main axes and
267 branches, mantle cell pattern, and cystidia) showed neither differences between both host species in our assay
268 nor deviations from reference descriptions of *T. melanosporum* ectomycorrhizae on various hosts (Zambonelli
269 et al. 1993; Rauscher et al. 1995, Rauscher and Chevalier 1995; De Miguel and Sáez 1997; Domínguez et al.
270 2005; Reyna and De Miguel 2007; Sáez and De Miguel 2008; Santelices and Palfner 2010). The application
271 of molecular tools (PCR, sequencing) allows not only confirmation of morphological mycorrhiza
272 identification but also helps to detect other fungal colonizers, especially similar but unwanted truffle species.
273 The ITS-rDNA region has been commonly employed for this purpose and has a large number of reference
274 sequences in major databases like GenBank or MycoBank (Henrion et al. 1994; Bertini et al. 1999; Giomaro
275 et al. 2002).

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277 The nurse plant method presented here is an efficient and real alternative for the inoculation of plants with *T.*
278 *melanosporum*. This method bases its success on the active mycorrhizal network that would exist at the root
279 system level. In addition, the management of substrate for the nursing of plants based on composted bark of
280 pine with pH correction is appropriate for the mycorrhiza formation with *T. melanosporum*. Some important
281 aspects of the nurse plant method remain to be studied: Can adventitious, unwanted ectomycorrhizal fungi be
282 permanently kept from replacing the truffle as the main colonizer of fine roots? Is there sustained vigor of
283 mycorrhizal formation during consecutive generations of nurse/nursling plants, and how many nurslings can
284 be inoculated or sustained by an individual nurse plant at a time? In this context, it would also be interesting
285 to test whether there is a net nutrient flux from the nurse plant (source) to the nurslings (sink) via the common

286 mycorrhizal network as has been reported for some associations (Selosse et al. 2006), and this would
287 constitute an additional benefit of this method, apart from the efficient formation of mycorrhizae.

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- 400

401 **Table 1** Chemical properties of pine bark substrate used for mycorrhization of *Quercus* spp. with *Tuber*
 402 *melanosporum* before (line 1) and after liming (line 2)

Liming	pH	OM (%)	N-NO ₃ mg Kg ⁻¹	P Olsen mg Kg ⁻¹	K mg Kg ⁻¹	Ca cmol Kg ⁻¹	Mg cmol Kg ⁻¹	CEC cmol Kg ⁻¹	C/N	EC dS m ⁻¹
Before	4.9	31.5	27.5	31.4	413.3	4.05	6.0	11.7	137.3	0.24
After	7.8	31.5	7.3	14.8	348.4	50.1	7.97	60.4	40.8	0.30

403 OM: organic matter; K available, Ca and Mg exchangeable, CEC: cation exchange capacity, EC: electric
 404 conductivity

405

406 **Figure Captions:**

407

408 **Fig. 1** a Relative mycorrhization of *Q. robur* nurse plants. b Relative mycorrhization of *Q. cerris* and *Q.*
409 *robur* nursling plants planted as acorns (A) and seedlings (S)

410 **Fig. 2** a Nurse plant setup; b mycorrhizal fine roots formed by *T. melanosporum* and *Q. cerris*; c-f
411 macroscopical and microscopical characteristics of ectomycorrhizae formed by *T. melanosporum*
412 and *Q. robur*: c monopodial mycorrhizal system with several cystidia (bar = 1 mm); d surface of
413 mycorrhizal root tip with cystidia and hyphae; e Segment of cystidium with simple septa and
414 orthogonal ramification (bar = 20µm); f outer layer of fungal mantle in plan view with
415 epidermoid-pseudoparenchymatous cell pattern

416 **Fig. 3** Diagnostic details of ectomycorrhizae formed by *T. melanosporum* and *Q. robur*; a Surface of fungal
417 mantle, consisting of a wide-meshed network of elongated and ramified hyphae, one of them
418 bearing a cystidium (arrowhead); b outer layer of fungal mantle (beneath a), forming an
419 epidermoid-pseudoparenchymatous cell pattern; c large cystidium with four orthogonally
420 arranged ramifications in lateral view, ramifications 2 and 4 bent by cover glass (schematic insert
421 indicating natural, tridimensional position of ramifications in view from top)

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